

A photograph of a tomato plant against a black background. The central part of the image shows a cluster of vibrant green, healthy-looking leaves with serrated edges. Above and below this central cluster, there are several brown, dried, and necrotic leaves, illustrating the impact of the endophytic Streptomyces on the host plant's growth and health.

Endophytic *Streptomyces* affect host growth and shape the endosphere microbiome of tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum*)

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Abstract

Plants coexist with a large diversity of microorganisms of which a sub-population can enter the endosphere. A selection of these endophytes are capable of plant growth promotion (PGP) by mechanisms such as phytostimulation, biofertilization or biocontrol. Supported by recent studies, *Streptomyces* sp. are likely major players in this endospheric community, containing potential PGP of commercial interest in the pursuit after more sustainable bio-applicants. The objective of this study is to investigate the link between *in vitro* screening of putative PGP traits and *in vivo* PGP in six endophytic *Streptomyces* strains (*S. griseolus*, *S. rishiriensis*, *S. exfoliatus*, *S. albiacialis*, *S. pratensis*) isolated from tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum* cv.). We verified that all strains except *S. rishiriensis* AC-107 and *S. griseolus* AC-34 have the capacity to actively enter the endosphere by secretion of cell-wall degrading enzymes. Seed inoculation with the strains had an extensive impact on the microbiome composition and diversity in the endosphere. None of the *Streptomyces* sp. strains were, however, observed to significantly promote plant growth or suppress *Verticillium* wilt disease *in vivo*. *S. griseolus* AC-34, nonetheless, consistently reduced *Verticillium dahliae* colonization *in vivo*. We observed a correlation between protease and chitinase, and this activity. Inability to re-isolate *S. griseolus* AC-34 infer that the strain is strictly confined to colonization of the root tissue. Our findings support the use of *In vitro* screenings as a tool to select potential PGP mode of action(s) to be further investigated. However, inclusion of a re-isolation verification step is emphasized.

Keywords: *Streptomyces*, endophyte, plant growth promotion, endophyte verification, endosphere microbiome, tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum*), *Verticillium dahliae*

1. Introduction

Plants live in close association with a large diversity of microorganisms. Demonstrated by decades of research on plant-microbe interactions occurring in the rhizosphere, these contribute to plant resistance to abiotic and biotic stresses (Berendsen et al., 2012). Despite the growing emphasis on the holistic study of the plant and its holobiome, our understanding of the non-pathogenic microbes residing within the plant remain limited (Vandenkoornhuysen et al., 2015). Orlando Petrini (1991) defined these endophytes as “all organisms inhabiting plant organs that at some time in their life cycle can colonize internal plant tissues without causing apparent harm to their host”.

Endophytes exploit a range of portals to enter the plant host, but it is commonly accepted that cracks forming in lateral root junctions are the primary site (Turner et al., 2014). Wounds, however, also present an alternative site of entry for a considerable number of endophytes. On the basis of their competence in gaining entry and to persistently colonizing the plants endosphere, Hardoim and Elsas (2008) separated endophytes in three types. i) **Passenger endophytes** which enters by accident at wounds and exhibit no competence in colonizing the endosphere. ii) **Opportunistic endophytes** which actively enters at root cracks by secretion of cell-wall degrading enzymes (CWDE), and exhibit competence in colonizing the endosphere for a shorter time span. iii) **Competent endophytes** which similarly gain entry actively at root cracks but exhibit competence to sustain a colonization of the endosphere, spread systemically by the vascular tissue and, in some cases, inhabit specific tissues. The lifestyle of most opportunistic and competent endophytes is facultative, alternating between soil and plant. Obligate competent endophytes, however, exist, completing their entire lifestyle within the plant and ensure transmission by an insect vector or vertically (Hardoim et al., 2008).

Consequential to the presented definition, endophytes interact with their plant hosts either as non-beneficial commensals or in some cases as mutualist. This latter subset of plant growth promoting endophytes (PGPE) are believed to exert their influence on the host plant by three mechanisms (Gaiero et al., 2013). i) **Phyostimulation** by biosynthesis of phytohormones or dampening abiotic stress response by lowering plant ethylene levels. ii) **Biofertilization** by enhancing accessibility of nutrients through e.g. fixation of atmospheric nitrogen or solubilisation of phosphorous. iii) **Biocontrol** by exerting an antagonistic effect on phytopathogens by e.g. biosynthesis of antibiotics, production of iron-chelating siderophores and secretion of chitinase or by induction of systemic resistance. These attributes make PGPE a potential candidate for the agro-industry as active component in bio-chemicals to reduce deployment of inorganic fertilizers and pesticides (Bonaldi et al., 2015; Viaene et al., 2016).

In the pursuit after PGPE, recent findings suggest *Streptomyces*, a ubiquitous Gram positive genus in the soil microbiome to likely contain such candidate species. *Streptomyces* is the largest genus within the Streptomycetaceae family, and phylum of Actinobacteria, comprising more than 500 species. Recognized for their large library of secondary metabolites, of which the majority exhibits antibiotic activity, *Streptomyces* derived bioactive metabolites can also stimulate plant growth (Viaene et al., 2016).

In a study by Lundberg and colleagues (2013), high-throughput analysis on *Arabidopsis thaliana* microbiomes demonstrated a significant enrichment of the Streptomycetaceae family in the endospheric compartment (Figure 1.1).

Figure 1.1: Histogram showing the distribution of phyla (A), and families within Actinobacteria (B) present in the 778 measurable operational taxonomic units in soil (S), rhizosphere (R) and endophytic compartment (EC) marked as enriched (↑) or depleted (↓) relative to soil in *Arabidopsis thaliana* ($n \geq 600$) grown in two geochemically distinct bulk soils. A differential number of asterisks above the diversity value represents a significant difference ($P < 0.05$). Taken from Lundberg et al. (2013).

The difference in microbiome composition between compartments, and reduced complexity in the endosphere, suggest either a recruitment of selected strains, plant tolerance to commensals or taxonomical groups inability to colonizing the endosphere (Lundberg et al., 2013). This enrichment points strongly toward *Streptomyces* sp. as central players in the endospheric microbiome, likely to include PGPE *Streptomyces* (PGPES) strains of commercial interest (Viaene et al., 2016).

The object of this MSc. thesis is to study the endophytic traits and PGP capacity of six *Streptomyces* strains isolated from tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum* cv.) xylem tissue. Strains will initially be screened on a range of indicator media for putative PGP traits. Secondly, PGP capacity is assessed by bioassays on tomato seedlings. A re-isolation assay will be conducted on harvested tomato seedlings to determine strains competence to persist within the endosphere. Thirdly, strains antagonistic activity of common fungal pathogens in the greenhouse production system of tomatoes is screened *in vitro*, with a biocontrol assay of Verticillium wilt disease *in vivo*. Conclusively, these experiments will allow us to address the questions; does a link exist between the initially screened putative PGP traits and the strains *in vivo* 1) PGP capacity, 2) persistency in the endosphere and 3) Biocontrol efficacy? We expect that a true PGPES exhibit several of the screened *in vitro* traits, demonstrates competence to persist in the endosphere, and consistently promotes plant growth in the assays.

2. Materials & Methods

2.1 Isolation of bacterial endophytes:

Tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum* cv. 1441, Piccolo, Mini Roma, Money Maker) cultivated organically was harvested at the end of greenhouse season in November 2015. Outer layer of collected stems was removed mechanically prior to a surface sterilization in 70% ethanol for four minutes followed by three subsequent wash with autoclaved tap-water. Xylem tissue was hereafter isolated, cut in small cubes (<5 mm) and grinded with 2 mL 1x phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) (g L⁻¹, 8; NaCl, 1.44; Na₂HPO₄, 0.24; KH₂PO₄, 0.2; KCl, pH 7.4) using pre-sterilized pestle and mortar. Extracted juice was plated in a dilution series of 10⁰ to 10⁻⁶ on TSB (g L⁻¹, 30; tryptic soy broth, 15; agar, pH 7.0) with 40 mg/L Delvocid[®]. Selection of *Streptomyces* sp. was done by addition of a 55°C incubation step for 30 minutes prior to plating.

2.2 Identification of isolates

To identify isolates, a single colony was picked for DNA extraction, dissolved in 100 µL autoclaved Milli-Q water and lysed at 95 °C for 15 minutes with two intermediate 1 minute cold-shock treatment on ice to ensure lysis of *Streptomyces* cells. Isolate 16S rRNA gene was hereafter amplified in a polymerase chain reaction (PCR), with the thermocycling conditions; 5 min at 95 °C, 35x (30s; 95 °C, 30s; 57 °C, 60s; 72 °C), 7 min at 72°C. Primers deployed were 1492R (5'-TACGGTTACCTTGTTACGACTT-3') and 27F (5'-AGAGTTTGATCATGGCTCA-3'). Successful amplification of isolate 16S rRNA gene (est. 1465 bp) was confirmed by running a agarose gel electrophoresis on the PCR product, visualized with ethidium bromide. Verified products were purified with an ExoSAP-IT[®] treatment and sent to sequencing at Eurofins Steins laboratory. Output was run through National Centre for Biotechnology Information (NCBI) Basic Local Alignment Search Tool (BLAST) database for identification of isolate taxonomy. For selected isolates PCR product was sent to sequencing with forward and reverse primer respectively, and collated with previous sequence data to generate a consensus sequence using Bioedit Sequence Alignment Editor (v7.0.9) software. This step reduces the likelihood of error in the sequence, and direct a more accurate BLAST comparison.

2.3 Growth conditions

Strains were cultured on tryptic soy broth (TSB) agar (g L⁻¹, 20; tryptic soy broth, 15; agar, pH 7.0) or in liquid cultures of 5 mL TSB and incubated in a shaking incubator at 28°C. Frozen stock of liquid cultures containing 25% glycerol were kept at -80°C.

2.4 In vitro screening of plant growth promoting traits

All 20 strains were screened on various indicator media as presented below by inoculating a 10 µL droplet of liquid TSB culture in three replicates. Purity test of liquid cultures were conducted prior to screening by spreading 100 µL of a 10⁻² dilution on TSB plates. Traits were scored visually according to relative size of clearing zones; none (-), minor (+) and large (++).

2.4.1 Biosynthesis of selected enzymes

Strains were screened for biosynthesis of chitinases, extracellular protease, DNase and the plant cell wall degrading enzymes cellulase, xylanase and pectinase. Cellulase biosynthesis was determined by inoculating strains on carboxymethylcellulose (CMC) agar (g L⁻¹, 10; peptone, 10; yeast extract, 10; carboxymethylcellulose-Na, 5; NaCl, 1; KH₂PO₄, 15; agar, pH 7.0)(Ghose, 1987). Xylanase and pectinase biosynthesis were determined by inoculating strains on a minimum media containing xylan (LMM) or pectin (PMM) respectively as sole carbon source (g L⁻¹, 1; pectin/xylan, 7; KH₂PO₄, 2.5; K₂HPO₄, 3; MgSO₄· 7H₂O, 2.5; NaCl, 0.1; (NH₄)₂SO₄, pH 8.0) (Beg et al., 2000). Chitinase biosynthesis was determined by inoculating strains on a colloidal chitin agar media (CCA) (g L⁻¹, 6; Na₂HPO₄, 3; KH₂PO₄, 1; NH₄Cl, 0.5; NaCl, 0.05; yeast extract, 10; colloidal chitin) in accordance with Hsu and Lockwood (1975) with modification in amount of colloidal chitin after Kuddus and Ahmad (2013). Clearing zones of CMC, LMM, PPM and CCA plates were visualized after 24 hours incubation by reversing plates, and addition of iodine beads to the lid for 10 minutes. Selected strains were equivalently inoculated on CCA plates in two replicates, and scored after 14 days of incubation without iodine bead stain. Biosynthesis of extracellular proteases was determined by inoculating strains on skimmed milk TSB (SKM-TSB) agar (g L⁻¹, 20; tryptic soy broth, 10; skimmed milk, pH 7.0). Clearing zones (i.e. without protein aggregates) were done after three days.

DNase biosynthesis of strains was determined by inoculation on Difco™ DNase test agar with methyl green (g L⁻¹, 10; tryptone, 10; proteose peptone no. 3, 5; NaCl, 2; deoxyribose acid, 0.05; methyl green, 15; agar, pH 7.3). Clearing zones were scored after three days.

2.4.2 Antagonistic activity

Strains were screened for their ability to inhibit pathogens common to the greenhouse production system of tomato, *Botrytis cinerea*, *Cladosporium fulvum*, *Fusarium oxysporum* f. sp. *lycopersici* and *Verticillium dahliae*. Antagonism of *B. cinerea* was determined by transferring a cube of 7 day old mycelium cultivated on potato dextrose agar (PDA) (g L⁻¹, 4; potato extract, 20; dextrose, 15; agar, pH 7.0) to the centre of a PDA + 0.5% yeast extract (YE) plate and subsequently inoculated it with the strains. Clearing zones were scored after three days. Antagonism of *C. fulvum*, *F. oxysporum* f. sp. *lycopersici* and *V. dahliae* was determined by preparing a solution of 10⁵ conidia or spores per mL harvested from 7 day old PDA plates using a haemocytometer. 100 µL of these solutions were spread by sterile glass beads on PDA + 0.5% YE plates, and left to dry for 15 minutes prior to inoculation of strains. Clearing zones were scored after three days.

2.4.3 Biosynthesis of compounds involved in nutrient acquisition

The solubilisation of phosphorous was initially assessed on pikovskayas (PVK) agar medium (g L⁻¹, 10; dextrose, 5; Ca₃(PO₄)₂, 0.5; yeast extract, 0.5; (NH₄)₂SO₄, 0.2; KCl, 0.1; MgSO₄ · 7H₂O, 1*10⁻⁴; MnSO₄ · H₂O, 1*10⁻⁴; FeSO₄ · 6H₂O, 15; agar, pH 7.0). Clearing zones were scored after seven days of incubation. Subsequently strains were inoculated on national botanic research institute's phosphate growth medium containing bromophenol blue (NBRIP-BPB) (g L⁻¹, 10; glucose, 5; Ca₃(PO₄)₂, 5; MgCl₂ · 6H₂O, 0.25; MgSO₄ · 7H₂O, 0.2g KCl, 0.1; (NH₄)₂SO₄, 0.025; bromophenol blue, pH 7.0) (Mehta and Nautiyal, 2001) to obtain a higher sensitivity. Observation of a yellow halo signifying a local acidification was done after three days of incubation and scored. The biosynthesis of siderophores was determined by inoculating strains on chrome azurol s (CAS) agar (100 mL Dye solution, 0.06; chrome azurol s, 0.073; Hexadecyltrimethylammoniumbromide (HDTMA), 0.0026; FeSO₄ · 6H₂O, 3.65*10⁻³; HCl) (Neilands, J. B and Schwyn, 1987) with an alternative xylem mimicking media (XMM) (g L⁻¹, 2.02; KNO₃, 2; Casamino acids, 1.233; MgSO₄, 1.168; NaCl, 0.147; CaCl₂, 0.022; KH₂PO₄, 0.056; K₂HPO₄, 1.5*10⁻⁶; FeSO₄, 15; agar, pH 7.0) (Hiery et al., 2015), here omitted from the iron component. An additional method was tested to circumvent the toxicity of HDTMA to particularly gram positive bacteria. Strains were, therefore, cultivated on XMM seven days prior to an overlay of 20 mL CAS (O-CAS) consisting of a 0.9% agar dye solution after Pérez-Miranda, S. and colleagues (2007). Observation of yellow halo signifying a sequestering of ferric iron was done after three days of incubation, and scored. Overlay of CAS was also done on selected strains grown on TSB to investigate siderophore production in a nutrient rich, complex media.

2.4.4 ACC Deaminase

Strains capacity to degrade 1-aminoacylpropane-1-carboxylic acid (ACC) by biosynthesis of an ACC deaminase was screened on DF salts minimal media (g L⁻¹, 2.0; (NH₄)₂SO₄, 4.0; KH₂PO₄, 6.0; Na₂HPO₄, 0.2; MgSO₄ · 7H₂O, 0.001; FeSO₄ · 7H₂O, 2.88*10⁻⁴; ZnSO₄ · 7H₂O, 1.96*10⁻⁴; CuSO₄ · 5H₂O, 5.72*10⁻⁵; H₃BO₃, 5.04*10⁻⁵; MnSO₄ · 7H₂O; 2.50*10⁻⁵; Na₂MoO₄ · 2H₂O, pH 7.0) (Dworkin and Foster, 1958) with 3 mM ACC as sole nitrogen source (Penrose and Glick, 2001). To validate the screening, inoculates were inoculated on a non-nitrogen containing DF salts media as negative, and a positive control with 2.02g/L KNO₃. Strains capable of growing on the DF salts + ACC media 7 days after inoculation were scored as ACC deaminase positive.

2.5 In vivo screening of plant growth promotion in cotton wool

A bioassay protocol was designed to screen the 20 strains for PGP capacity in tomato (cv. Moneymaker) at two inoculum densities. Each treatment combination was done in five replicates on a Styrofoam block (15x7x4.5 cm) of 10 holes (2.5 cm diameter) per strain. Growth boxes (20x20x6 cm) contained two blocks of which one was placed in a tray to prevent strain cross-contamination.

To remove surface bacteria the tomato seeds were treated with a 2.5% hypochlorite solution for 30 minutes and washed three times with autoclaved tap water. The seeds were hereafter placed in rows of 8x8 on heat sterilized, pre-wetted tissue paper in a square Petri dish and cold treated at 4°C for two days. Thereafter the seeds received a four day dark-treatment at room temperature to stimulate germination by wrapping petri dishes in aluminium foil. Seeds exhibiting a (>4mm) root with fine root hairs were carefully transplanted to heat sterilized and pre-

watered cotton plugs in each block. Prior to the assay growth boxes and blocks were sterilized with a wash of 70% ethanol, and left to dry for one day with a closed lid. The optical density (OD) of strain liquid cultures was measured at 600 nm in a 10^1 dilution to facilitate preparations of 10^4 CFU and 10^8 CFU suspensions, with the conversion factor of 1 OD₆₀₀ corresponding to 8×10^8 CFU (Myers et al., 2013). In each block the left row of five seeds received the low concentration inoculum, and right row the high concentration. Strain cultures producing large beads hindering measurement of OD₆₀₀ were inoculated at 50 μ L and 100 μ L of undiluted liquid culture, transferring at minimum one bead. Negative control was treated with autoclaved tap water.

Cultivation of tomato seedlings was done in a growth chamber (10h photoperiod at 21°C, 14 h dark period at 19°C and 70% relative humidity) and bottom of tray/box kept watered with autoclaved tap water. Seven days after transplantation and onward 10% Hoagland (Hoagland and Arnon, 1950) or tomaat 2.0 EC tap water solution (g L⁻¹, NH₄; 0.022, K; 0.282, Ca; 0.160, Mg; 0.044, NO₃; 0.769, SO₄; 0.319, Fe; 1.95×10^{-3} , Mn; 4.40×10^{-4} , Zn; 3.27×10^{-4} , B; 2.16×10^{-4} , Cu; 3.18×10^{-5} , Mo; 4.80×10^{-5} , pH 5.5) was used. 24 days after transplantation seedling were harvested separately in rows per strain according to inoculum density and fresh weight (FW) of each seedling was measured. Assay was conducted in replicate at inoculum density of 10^8 CFU with six seedlings per treatment combination under different growth chamber conditions (12h photoperiod at 19°C, 12 h dark period at 17°C and 70% relative humidity) used for the remaining bioassays. Seedlings were harvested after 39 days.

2.5.1 Re-isolation of inoculated strains

Competence of strains to persist within the tomato endosphere was assessed in a re-isolation assay on surface sterilized stem and second leaves separately after FW measurement by plating a dilution series of tissue extract. Stem sections of 2-3 mm were removed on the root side to ensure isolation of true stem colonizing bacteria, and pooled in rows of each treatment combination in Eppendorf tubes. These were then sterilized in 70% ethanol for 10 minutes and washed three times in autoclaved tap water. One second leaf was selected per seedling and pooled in rows of each treatment combination in a 50 mL falcon tube and surface sterilized in 70% ethanol for 2 minutes and washed three times with autoclaved tap water. Hereafter stems and leaves were crushed in 200 μ L 1x PBS with an Eppendorf pestle. Tissue extract were plated in a dilution series of 10^0 , 10^{-2} and 10^{-3} 1x PBS solution, spread by glass beads on TSB + 40 mg/L delvolid® plates and incubated for one week. Visual identification of strain colony morphology was hereafter done an identity determined by 16S rRNA gene sequence. In replicate assay only the stem section was used for re-isolation.

2.5.2 PCR guided identification of inoculated strains

DNA from the stem extraction juice was purified from salts, proteins and other organic components by treatment of phenol-chloroform-isoamylalcohol (24:24:1), chloroform and isopropanol with intermediary centrifugations. A modified 16S rRNA gene amplification PCR protocol was hereafter conducted utilizing Streptomyces specific primers StrepB-F (5'-ACAAGCCCTGGAAACGGGT-3') and StrepE-R (5'-CACCAGGAATTCCGATCT-3') at an annealing temperature of 54°C (Rintala et al., 2001). Primer specificity was tested on all present strain genus to validate results, and PCR products were visualized by gel electrophoresis.

2.6 Selection of strains for further study

Streptomyces sp. and strains of particular performance in the initial plant growth promotion bioassay were selected for further *in vitro* and *in vivo* studies.

2.7 In vivo screening of selected strains plant growth promotion in soil

An additional bioassay was conducted in potting soil medium (40.6 kg; Horti clay, 3.3kg; Dolokal extra potting soil, 0.3m³; Common peat, 0.2m³; MD Swedish sphagnum peat, 0.3m³; Baltic peat, 0.2m³; Structure bark, 0.81kg; Yara PG Mix 15+10+20; pH \approx 5.7, Electric conductivity \approx 0.8) to assess selected strains capacity to persist and promote growth in more natural settings. Setup of the bioassay was similar to the previous on cotton wool with few modifications. Seedlings were transplanted to plastic square pots (7x7x9 cm) containing soil pre-wetted with autoclaved tap water and inoculated with 1 mL 10^8 CFU solution of strain liquid culture. Each strain treatment was conducted in replicate of nine. Tomato seedlings were harvested 28 days after transplantation, FW measured and above pictures processed in ImageJ software to calculate leaf coverage as a measure of PGP. Roots were washed clean to visualize any substantial change in root architecture as an indication of PGP in the below ground apartment. Lastly, stem sections (\approx 5 cm) were cut for each plant and surface sterilized for 10 minutes in 70% ethanol. Central section (\approx 4mm) of each surface sterilized stem was placed in a pre-sterilized 2 mL screwcap

tube containing 2-3 metal beads, added 200 µL 1xPBS and crushed using a mixer mill at 30 Hz for 3 minutes. Tubes were weighed prior to the addition of plant material, and after, to enable an estimation of endophytic population per g FW from the dilution series plating. Stem extraction juice was hereafter plated in a dilution series and incubated as previously described. An estimation of endophytic population was done according to the formula below, with V being the volume of buffer solution and FW of plant material.

$$\text{Estimated population} = \text{Colony Count} * \text{dilution factor} * \frac{V}{0.100}$$

2.8: Suppression assay of selected strains on Verticillium wilt disease

The capacity of selected strains to suppress Verticillium wilt disease was assessed in a tomato seedling assay similar to the PGP setup in soil presented above. Infection was done by inoculating carefully uprooted and washed 10 day old tomato seedlings roots for 10 minutes in a 10⁶ spore solution of *V. dahliae* JR2 harvested from 7 day old plates, and re-planting them. Negative control was treated similarly, however, inoculated with water instead of an endophyte or *V. dahliae* solution. Mock treatment was inoculated with *V. dahliae* solely. Plants were harvested 23 days after infection, FW measured, above pictures taken and stem section weighed for re-isolation of inoculated strains. A replicate of the suppression assay was conducted and harvested 36 days after *V. dahliae* inoculation.

2.8.1 Fungal recovery assay

Semi-quantitative assessment of *V. dahliae* infection was done by surface sterilizing the stem section just below the second leaves (≈ 3 cm) of each plant in 10% hypochlorite for 5 minutes, and 70% ethanol for 5 minutes. Ends of stems were hereafter removed and five transection slides per plant were plated on PDA + 34 mg/L chloroamphenicol. Growth of *V. dahliae* was categorized as 0 (none), 1 (minor), 2 (Intermediate) or 3 (large) after 4 days of incubation at 28°C. Sterilization protocol in replicate assay was adjusted to 10 minutes instead of 5 in 10% hypochlorite and 70% ethanol respectively to inhibit growth of unwanted epi- and endophytic fungi. For all strain treatments except *S. griseolus* AC-34 and *S. rishiriensis* AC-107 plus controls, two plants were kept for further microbiome studies, above picture was, however, still taken of these.

2.9 Statistical analysis

Paired t-test analysis was conducted on all FW, leaf coverage measurements and fungal recovery data with a significance threshold of $P \leq 0.05$ using IBM SPSS statistical software package ver. 22.

3. Results

3.1 Isolation of bacterial endophytes

Plating of extraction juice from surface sterilized tomato xylem resulted in the isolation of 81 cultivable bacterial endophytes, of which 20 were selected as initial material for this project (Table 3.2).

3.2 Identification of isolates

Identification of isolates by an NCBI BLAST® database comparison of 16S rRNA gene, grouped six isolates as *Streptomyces* sp. and six as *Bacillus* sp. with the rest belonging to the genus of *Nocardiopsis*, *Micrococcus Brevibacterium* and *Collimonas* (Table 3.2).

Table 3.2: Identity of 20 bacterial endophytic isolates by 16S rRNA gene sequence comparison in NCBI BLAST® database, and origin of isolation from surface sterilized tissue

Strain	Identity	Origin	
		Tissue	<i>Solanum lycopersicum</i> cv.
AC-34	<i>Streptomyces griseolus</i>	Root	<i>Money maker</i>
AC-35	<i>Bacillus amylolyquefaciens</i> sups. <i>plantarum</i>	Leaf	<i>Money maker</i>
AC-107	<i>Streptomyces rishiriensis</i>	Leaf	Unknown
AC-109	<i>Streptomyces exfoliatus</i>	Leaf	Unknown
AC-116	<i>Bacillus amylolyquefaciens</i> sups. <i>plantarum</i>	- ¹	Unknown
NE-8	<i>Bacillus kochii</i>	Stem xylem	1441
NE-10	<i>Micrococcus yunnanensis</i>	Stem xylem	<i>Piccolo</i>
NE-1141-2	<i>Streptomyces albiacialis</i>	Stem xylem	1441
NE-1141-6	<i>Nocardinopsis listeri</i>	Stem xylem	1441
NE-1141-7	<i>Streptomyces pratensis</i>	Stem xylem	1441
NE-P-5	<i>Brevibacterium iodinum</i>	Stem xylem	<i>Piccolo</i>
NE-P-8	<i>Streptomyces pratensis</i>	Stem xylem	<i>Piccolo</i>
NE-MR-5	<i>Nocardinopsis listeri</i>	Stem xylem	<i>Mini Roma</i>
NE-MR-10	<i>Nocardinopsis coralliicola</i>	Stem xylem	<i>Mini Roma</i>
FF-15	<i>Bacillus amylolyquefaciens</i> sups. <i>plantarum</i>	Stem xylem	<i>Mini Roma</i>
FF-18	<i>Bacillus thuringiensis</i>	Stem xylem	<i>Piccolo</i>
OA-1	<i>Bacillus thuringiensis</i>	Stem xylem	<i>Piccolo</i>
OA-MR-3	<i>Nocardinopsis prasina</i>	Stem xylem	<i>Mini Roma</i>
ZI-3	<i>Bacillus cytotoxicus</i>	Stem xylem	<i>Piccolo</i>
MEE-I-1	<i>Collimonas pratensis</i>	Stem xylem	Unknown

¹ Spontaneous contamination giving halo on *Trichoderma viride*

3.4 *In vitro* screening of plant growth promotion traits

Several enzymes, compounds involved in nutrient acquisition and antagonistic activity towards phytopathogens has been proposed as traits of PGP by bacterial endophytes. Strains were, therefore, screened on indicator media for a selection of these traits (Table 3.4).

3.4.1 Biosynthesis of selected enzymes

To assess the strains ability to biosynthesise selected enzymes related to PGP, these were screened on six different indicator media (Figure 3.4.1). Among the strains, a high production of CWDE was common, with six (30%) strains not showing the capacity to degrade cellulose and, four strains (20%) not capable of degrading xylan or pectin (Table 3.4). The ability to degrade chitin was observed in majority of strains, with 13 (65%) displaying a larger degree, two (10%) minor and five (25%) incapable. In the screening conducted on selected strains, *S. griseolus* AC-34, *S. albiacialis* NE-1141-2 and *S. pratensis* NE-1141-7 were observed to exhibit the highest production of chitinase. All strains were found to produce extracellular proteases, with an equal division between large and minor category. Production of extracellular DNase was observed in 15 (75%), with only three strains displaying a larger production. Common for all *Streptomyces* sp. strains were the ability to produce CWDE, chitinase and extracellular proteases.

Figure 3.4.1: Indicator media for screening of bacterial biosynthesis of selected enzymes. Plates are displayed as examples of the scored phenotypes.

- A:** Carboxymethylcellulose agar, for cellulase
- B:** Pectin minimal media, for pectinase
- C:** Xylan minimal media, for xylanase
- D:** Colloidal chitin agar, for chitinase
- E:** Skimmed milk TSB, for extracellular proteases
- F:** Difco™ DNase test agar, for extracellular DNases.

Table 3.4: *in vitro* screening results of putative plant growth promoting traits of 20 endophytic bacterial strains from tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum* cv.). Strains are scored accordingly; no clearing zone (-), small clearing zone (+), large clearing zone (++) with $n \geq 3$. Score represent the average, rounding up to the nearest score category. Numbers in superscript specify the number of replicates of each screening where $n < 3$.

Strain	Biosynthesis of selected enzymes						Antagonistic activity versus					
	Cellulase	Pectinase	Xylanase	Chitinase	Extracellular protease	DNase	<i>Verticillium dahliae</i>	<i>Fusarium oxysporum</i> f.sp. <i>lycopersici</i>	<i>Cladosporium fulvum</i>	<i>Botrytis cinerea</i>	Siderophore production	<i>P. solubilization</i>
AC-34	++	++	++	++	++	+	+	-	+	++	+	-
AC-35	++	++	++	++	++	+	+	+	++	+	+	++
AC-107	++	++	+	++	+	-	-	-	+	-	++	-
AC-109	++	++	++	++	+	+	++	-	+	+	+	-
AC-116	++	++	++	++	++	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
NE-8	-	+	+	+	++	++	+	+	+	+	+	+
NE-10	-	+	+	-	+	+	- ²	-	-	-	++	-
NE-1141-2	++	++	++	++	++	-	-	-	+	-	++	-
NE-1141-6	-	+	+	+	+	-	+	-	-	-	+	-
NE-1141-7	+	++	++	++	++	-	+	-	+	++	++	-
NE-P-5	-	-	-	-	+	+	-	-	-	-	+	-
NE-P-8	++	++	++	++	+	+	+	-	+	+	+	-
NE-MR-5	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	-	-	-	++	-
NE-MR-10	-	-	-	-	+	+	++ ²	-	- ¹	-	+ ²	-
FF-15	++	++	++	++	++	+	++	+	++	++	+	++
FF-18	++	++	++	++	++	++	++	-	-	-	+	-
OA-1	++	++	++	++	++	++	++	+	+	+	+	-
OA-MR-3	+	++	++	++	++	+	++ ²	-	-	-	++	+
ZI-3	++	++	++	++	+	+	+	-	-	-	+	-
MEE-I-1	++ ²	- ¹	- ¹	- ¹	+ ²	+	- ¹	- ¹	- ¹	+ ²	++	+

3.4.2 Antagonistic activity

To assess the strains capacity to antagonize common fungal pathogens found in the greenhouse production system of tomato, strains were co-cultured with a selected four of these. The ability to inhibit *V. dahliae* growth was a common trait amongst the strains (Figure 3.4.2A), while half showed antagonistic activity towards *Cladosporium fulvum* and *Botrytis cinerea* (Figure 3.4.2C, D). *Fusarium oxysporum* f.sp *lycopersici* was, however, only antagonized

by *B. amyloliquefaciens* AC-35, AC-116, FF-15, *B. kochii* NE-8 and *B. thuringiensis* OA-1 (Figure 3.4.2B). These five *Bacillus* sp. strains showed the highest antagonistic capacity in the screening, capable of inhibiting the growth of all four pathogens. The ability to antagonize a phytopathogen was a common trait in the endophytic strains, and only a *Brevibacterium iodinum* NE-P-5 showed none.

Figure 3.4.2: Screening of endophytic bacterial strains antagonistic activity towards **A:** *Verticillium dahliae*, **B:** *Fusarium oxysporum f.sp lycopersici* **C:** *Cladosporium fulvum* **D:** *Botrytis cinerea*. Plates are displayed as examples of the scored phenotypes.

3.4.3 Biosynthesis of compounds involved in nutrient acquisition

Strains were screened for their ability to solubilize phosphate, and hence provide a beneficial effect to the host plant by enhancing the availability. Six strains (30%) were observed to solubilize phosphate, of which the *B. amyloliquefaciens* AC-35 and FF-15 demonstrated the highest degree (3.4.3A). The strains were equally screened for production of siderophores, iron chelating compounds believe to either enhance availability of iron for the host plant, or limit the availability for e.g. phytopathogens. All strains were found to produce siderophores on XMM with seven (35%) strains showing a high degree (Figure 3.4.3B). Selected strains *B. amyloliquefaciens* AC-35, *S. exfoliatus* AC-109, *S. pratensis* NE-1141-7 and NE-P-8 demonstrated a high production of siderophores on TSB media (Figure 3.4.3C). Conclusively, production of siderophores was common amongst the 20 endophytic strains, solubilisation of phosphorous, however, a more rare trait.

Figure 3.4.3: Screening of endophytic bacterial strains production of putative plant growth promoting compounds. **A:** NBRIP-BPB plate, phosphate solubilisation Overlay of chrome azurol s (O-CAS) dye agar for visualization of siderophore production on **B:** xylem mimicking media **C:** TSB, for selected strains strains. Plates are displayed as examples of the scored phenotypes.

3.4.4 ACC Deaminase

Degradation of ACC, a precursor to the phytohormone ethylene by ACC deaminase, has been proposed to exert a substantial role in PGP by dampening stress response. Strains were, therefore, screened on a DF salts minimal media with ACC as sole nitrogenous source, alongside a positive control media with KNO_3 and a negative control not containing an N-source. All strains were observed to grow on the negative control, clouding any results observed in the assay.

3.5 *In vivo* screening of plant growth promotion in cotton wool

The screening of strains PGP capacity was initially conducted on a tomato seedling-cotton wool setup, and harvested after 24 days (Figure 3.51). Amongst the strains, *M. yunnanensis* NE-10 and *S. rishiriensis* AC-107 demonstrated a significant difference in mean FW, however, negative (figure 3.51A). This existence of a strain specific detrimental effect on plant FW was not confirmed in replicate bioassay (figure 3.51B). All strains displaying brown fungal growth on cotton plug, a contamination likely originating from the growth chamber, showed a consistent negative trend. The *B. amyloliquefaciens* AC-35 and *B. thuringiensis* OA-1 demonstrated a positive trend in mean FW, and the *Brevibacterium* iodinum NE-P-5 a less consistent effect. Inoculation with *Streptomyces* sp. did not show any solid trend, *S. albiacialis* NE-1141-2, nonetheless displayed the highest mean FW in replicat assay (Table 3.5).

Figure 3.51: Fresh weight (FW) of tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum* cv. Moneymaker) seedlings cultivated on cotton wool after seed inoculation with endophytic strain. **A:** Initial bioassay, pooled FW of five seedlings inoculated with 10^4 CFU, and 5 seedlings with 10^8 CFU. Harvested after 24 days. **B:** Replicate bioassay, six seedlings inoculated with 10^8 CFU. Harvested after 39 days.

Negative control treated with water, n = 10.

3.5.1 Re-isolation of inoculated strains

To validate if the strains were true endophytes of tomato, capable of colonizing and persisting within the endosphere, a re-isolation assay was conducted on surface sterilized stem and leaf material at harvest. Plates of extraction juice was incubated and thereafter examined for bacterial colonies displaying the morphology of the original inoculated strain. Eight strains (42%) were successfully re-isolated and verified to genus level by 16S rRNA gene sequence comparison in the initial bioassay, including four *Streptomyces* sp., *S. exfoliatus* AC-109, *S. albiacialis* NE-1141-2, *S. pratensis* NE-1141-7 and NE-P-8. Extraction plates with *B. amyloliquefaciens* AC-35 and FF-15 inoculated seedlings produced colonies of similar morphology to the original but 16S rRNA sequence result showed in both cases to be *Paenibacillus xylanexedens*. The confirmed re-isolated strain showed no general tissue specificity in the initial bioassay, with four strains found both in stem and leaf, and two in either stem or leaf solely. The negative control displayed a large diversity of cultivable endophytic bacteria (Figure 3.5.1A). Seedlings inoculated with e.g. *B. amyloliquefaciens* AC-116, *B. thuringiensis* FF-18 and *S. exfoliatus* AC-109 (Figure 3.5.1B), however, exhibited a low diversity, with high abundance of the inoculated strain. Some strains were unsuccessfully re-isolated, but still exhibited a very different microbiome composition in comparison to negative control, *S. pratensis* NE-P-8 is an extreme case of this (Figure 3.5.1C).

Figure 3.5.1: Plating of stem extraction juice from the initial tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum* cv. MoneyMaker) seedling plant growth promotion bioassay in cotton wool to re-isolate inoculated strains.

A: Negative control (100 μ L undiluted plating)

B: AC-109 (100 μ L undiluted plating)

C: NE-P-8 (100 μ L undiluted plating)

In the replicate assay seven (35%) strains were re-isolated based on colony morphology, of which *B. thuringiensis* OA-1 and FF-18 were among the eight strains previously verified to genus level by 16S rRNA gene comparison. However, none of the *Streptomyces* sp. strains were re-isolated. Seedlings inoculated with *B. thuringiensis* FF-18, OA-1 and *B. amyloliquefaciens* FF-15 exhibited a low diversity microbiome consistent with the results observed in the initial bioassay. An immediate result of the re-isolation assay was the extensive difference in culturable endophytic bacteria between various strain inoculations and the negative control.

3.5.2 PCR guided identification of inoculated strains

In addition to visual identification of the inoculated strains, a PCR guided step was included, deploying *Streptomyces* sp. specific primers in a modified 16S rRNA PCR protocol. Purpose of this step was to increase the accuracy of which inoculated *Streptomyces* sp. could be validated in the extraction juice samples. In the assay *Streptomyces* sp., *S. rishiriensis* AC-107, *S. exfoliatus* AC-109, *S. pratensis* NE-1141-7 and *S. pratensis* NE-P-8 were validated (Figure 3.5.2). Specificity control of the *Streptomyces* specific primers on all strain genus, however, revealed an amplification of *Micrococcus* sp. 16S rRNA gene (Figure 3.5.2, C11). In several of the extraction juice samples originating from plants inoculated with non-*Streptomyces* sp. an amplification product was observed, including *B. amyloliquefaciens* AC-35, AC-116, *B. kochii* NE-8, *M. yunnanensis* NE-10 and *N. listeri* NE-1141-6. Identification of non-strain colonies from re-isolation plates by 16S rRNA gene sequence comparison, however, revealed a *Micrococcus aloevera* (Distinct non-glossy yellow colony). Primer un-specificity is, therefore, likely giving cause to false validation of *Streptomyces* sp. in samples with a low band intensity. Despite these false positives, the PCR guided identification step still provide a valuable piece of information in the validation of true endophytic behaviour of the strains. Moreover, if additional specificity is desired, a digestion step with an *Bst*YI restriction endonuclease will produce a *Streptomyces* specific cleavage product of 567 and 507 bp (Rintala et al., 2001).

Table 3.5: Fresh weight and re-isolation results of endophytic bacterial strains in the tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum* cv. Moneymaker) seedling bioassay in cotton wool 24 days (initial), and 39 days (replicate) after inoculation. Paired t-test was conducted on strain mean relative to Neg. control with $P \leq 0.05$. S = Stem. L = Leaf. * = Cotton plug showing symptoms of fungal growth.

Strain	Bioassay 1						Replicate			
	Fresh Weight ($n = 10$)			Re-isolation			Fresh Weight ($n = 6$)			Re-isolation
	Mean (g)	Standard Deviation	Paired t-test p value	Morphological visualization	Organ colonized	16S rRNA gene Identity Consensus	Mean (g)	Standard deviation	Paired t-test p value	Stem colonization
AC-34	Not tested						0.090*	0.04	0.01	–
AC-35	0.225	0.15	0.358	+	S,L	–	0.235	0.07	0.327	+
AC-107	0.122*	0.07	0.013	–			0.166	0.12	0.812	–
AC-109	0.154	0.12	0.391	+	S,L	+	0.154	0.07	0.597	–
AC-116	0.190	0.12	0.962	+	L	+	0.134*	0.07	0.216	–
NE-8	0.166	0.11	0.759	+	S,L	–	0.139	0.11	0.525	+
NE-10	0.094*	0.07	0.035	–			0.207 b	0.17	0.730	+
NE-1141-2	0.147	0.05	0.283	+	S,L	+	0.305	0.24	0.194	–
NE-1141-6	0.214	0.15	0.647	+	S	–	0.222	0.14	0.612	–
NE-1141-7	0.155*	0.09	0.634	+	L	+	0.100*	0.05	0.026	–
NE-P-5	0.205	0.14	0.773	–			0.289	0.17	0.145	+
NE-P-8	0.187	0.08	0.967	+	S	+	0.185	0.21	0.946	–
NE-MR-5	0.174	0.12	0.889	–			0.225	0.09	0.383	–
NE-MR-10	0.158	0.05	0.311	–			0.081*	0.05	0.056	–
FF-15	0.157	0.13	0.460	+	S,L	–	0.222	0.05	0.252	+
FF-18	0.133	0.08	0.145	+	S,L	+	0.142	0.08	0.245	+
OA-1	0.252	0.08	0.161	+	S,L	+	0.264	0.14	0.275	+
OA-MR-3	0.193	0.05	0.733	+	L	–	0.204	0.20	0.815	–
ZI-3	0.216	0.12	0.562	–			0.143	0.09	0.501	–
MEE-I-1	0.213	0.20	0.607	+	S	+	0.127	0.10	0.370	–
Neg. Control	0.188*	0.09					0.149 $n = 10$	0.08		

Figure 3.5.2: PCR guided identification of *Streptomyces* sp. in stem extraction juice from the initial tomato (*S. lycopersicum* cv. Moneymaker) seedling bioassay in cotton wool 24 days after inoculation with strains in low 10^4 CFU (L) or high 10^8 CFU (R) dosage, visualized by agarose gel electrophoresis

C 1-4: Pure colony 16S rRNA of 1; *Bacillus* sp., 2; *Streptomyces* sp. 3; *Micrococcus* sp. 4; *Nocardiopsis* sp.

C 5-8: 16S rRNA amplification on DNA extraction of seeds inoculated with above stated strains

C 9-12: Strept E/B specific primers on DNA extraction of seeds inoculated with above stated strains

C13: Negative control, 16S rRNA mastermix

C14: Negative control, Strept E/B primer mastermix

3.6 Selection of strains for further study

In order to obtain a more thorough *in vivo* study of strains PGP capacity and ability to suppress Verticillium wilt disease a selection step was conducted. All *Streptomyces* sp., *S. griseolus* AC-34, *S. rishiriensis* AC-107, *S. exfoliatus* AC-109, *S. albiacialis* NE-1141-2, *S. pratensis* NE-1141-7 and *S. pratensis* NE-P-8 were selected for further study. The *Bacillus* sp., *B. amyloliquefaciens* AC-35 and *B. thuringiensis* OA-1 were equally selected based on indication of PGP capacity in the initial assay, and re-isolation results.

3.7 In vivo screening of selected strains plant growth promotion in soil

To investigate the strains PGP capacity in tomato plants cultivated in soil, and their ability to persist in a more diverse endospheric microbiome a second bioassay was conducted on the selected strains. In the assay, *S. griseolus* AC-34 was found as the only strain to have a significant effect on mean FW, reducing it. Other strains, *S. rishiriensis* AC-107 and *S. albiacialis* NE-1141-2 showed a negative trend in mean FW, whereas *S. exfoliates* AC-109 and *B. thuringiensis* OA-1 a positive trend (figure 3.7B, C). Measurement of leaf coverage revealed the same distributional pattern as FW, without any strains significantly differing (Figure 3.7A). Larger spread was observed in plant size of the negative control, *B. amyloliquefaciens* AC-35, and *S. griseolus* AC-34 had a single outlier. To assess if the strains had an influence on the below ground apartment, roots of three plants per treatment were rinsed. Slight differences were observed in root architecture, with two groupings, 1; short, more branched roots such as *B. amyloliquefaciens* AC-35, and 2; longer, less branched roots such as *S. exfoliatus* AC-109 and *S. pratensis* NE-P-8 (Figure 3.7D).

3.7.1 Re-isolation of inoculated strain

In the assay, four (50%) of the strains were re-isolated based on colony morphology, *S. exfoliatus* AC-109, *S. albiacialis* NE-1141-2, *S. pratensis* NE-1141-7 and *B. thuringiensis* OA-1 (Table 3.7 in supplementary material). Total population of cultivable endophytes were found to be in the interval $3.01 * 10^2$ to $5.9 * 10^3$ colony forming units (CFU) per gram FW. In comparison to the previous re-isolation assays, the number of colonies and diversity of microorganisms observed was visually lower.

Figure 3.7: illustration of endophytic bacterial strains plant growth promoting capacity by measurements on **A:** Leaf coverage. **B:** Fresh weight (FW), in a tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum* cv. Moneymaker) seedling bioassay in potting soil 28 days after seed inoculation. Pictures of plant height (**C**) and roots (**D**) at harvest. Mean values followed by the same letters do not significantly differ from negative control based on paired t-test at $P \leq 0.05$. $n = 9$. Bars represent standard deviation.

3.8 Suppression assay of selected strains on Verticillium wilt disease

Assay was conducted to investigate if the endophytic strains were capable of suppressing Verticillium wilt disease. Tomato seedlings treated with the selected strains were infected with *V. dahliae* spores after 10 days, and measurement of FW, leaf coverage and a fungal recovery assay was done at harvest 23 days after infection. The Verticillium wilt disease inflicted a reduction in average mean fresh weight from 4.469g to 2.448g (45.22%) between negative control and mock treatment (Table 3.81 in supplementary material). Average leaf coverage was similarly reduced from 149.6 cm² to 84.67 cm² (43.40%), and observed to follow the same distributional pattern as FW (Figure 3.81B, C). Seedlings treated with *S. rishiriensis* AC-107 displayed a significantly higher leaf coverage and fresh weight. Whereas *S. griseolus* AC-34, *B. amylolyquefaciens* AC-35 and *B. thuringiensis* OA-1 displayed a minor positive tendency. Moreover, a large variability was observed in FW and leaf coverage results of strain treatments relative to mock and negative control. In order to connect a changes in FW and leaf coverage of a strain treatment to mock, a re-isolation assay was conducted to verify the presence of the inoculated strains. However, the assay failed due to a contaminated PBS solution.

The replicate assay was harvested 36 days after root inoculation with *V. dahliae* spores. In consistence with previous observations, a reduction of 6.963g to 4.003g (42.52%) in average mean FW was observed between negative control and mock (Table 3.8). Leaf coverage was reduced from a mean of 203.8 cm² to 139 cm² (31.83%) between negative control and mock treatment. Two plants per treatment were removed for further microbiome studies, and might have given cause to the less strong relation observed between FW and leaf coverage. Seedlings treated with *B. thuringiensis* OA-1 were the only to exhibit a leaf coverage significantly different from the mock treatment, whereas *S. pratensis* NE-P-8 showed a positive tendency on mean

leaf coverage. Strain treatments *B. thuringiensis* OA-1, *S. albiacialis* NE-1141-2 and *S. pratensis* NE-1141-7, however, showed a positive tendency on mean FW. *S. pratensis* NE-1141-7 was the only inoculant to be re-isolated, with only few colonies exhibiting the morphological identity of the original inoculant.

Figure 3.81: Illustration of endophytic strains capacity to suppress *Verticillium* wilt disease by assessment of **A:** Fungal recovery. **B:** Leaf Coverage. **C:** Fresh weight (FW), in the first tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum* cv. Moneymaker) seedling bioassay in potting 33 days after seed inoculation, and 23 days after root dip in *Verticillium dahliae* spores solution. **D:** Side pictures of a selected representative plant for each strains treatment at harvest. Mean values followed by the same letters do not significantly differ from Mock treatment based on paired t-test at $P \leq 0.05$. $n = 9$. Mock is solely inoculated with *V. dahliae*.

3.8.1 Fungal recovery assay

In order to semi-quantitatively assess the *V. dahliae* infection, five transection slides of surface sterilized stem were plated per plant and fungal growth was scored after four days. Seedlings treated with strain *S. griseolus* AC-34 demonstrated the only significant difference, with a positive reduction in fungal growth, while *S. pratensis* NE-P-8 and *B. thuringiensis* OA-1 displayed a minor positive tendency (Figure 3.81A). Unsubstantial tissue sterilization, however, cloud the results as growth of miscellaneous endophytic and epiphytic fungi was observed in the negative control, exhibiting a mean fungal recovery value of 1.15. In the replicate assay, a longer sterilization was applied, lowering fungal recovery value of the negative control from 1.15 to 0.69 relative to the first assay (Table 3.8, Table 3.81 in supplementary material). No significant difference was observed in fungal recovery value of strain treatments in the replicate assay. However, *S. griseolus* AC-34 exhibited a positive trend in reduction of in fungal growth and AC-109 a negative trend. *S. griseolus* AC-34 was, therefore, the only strain to show moderate capacity to suppress *Verticillium* wilt disease.

Table 3.8: Fresh weight, Leaf coverage, disease severity and re-isolation results of the replicate tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum* cv. Moneymaker) – *Verticillium* wilt disease suppression bioassay in soil 36 days after seed inoculation with endophytic strain, and 26 days after root dip in *Verticillium dahliae* JR2 spore solution. Paired t-test was conducted on strain mean relative to Mock treatment with $P \leq 0.05$. Mock is inoculated with *V. dahliae* solely.

Strain	Fresh weight				Leaf Coverage				Fungal Recovery				Re-isolation	
	Mean (g)	SD	Paired t-test p-value	n	Mean (cm ²)	SD	Paired t-test p-value	n	Mean	SD	Paired t-test p-value	n	Stem colonization	Total Population size Per g FW
AC-34	4.183	1.15	0.382	9	117.28	33.2	0.275	9	1.53	0.53	0.225	9	-	1.51 * 10 ²
AC-35	3.505	1.56	0.501	7	147.96	82.6	0.902	8	1.93	0.33	0.679	6	-	-
AC-107	4.095	1.00	0.751	9	134.04	46.7	0.811	9	1.73	0.58	0.613	9	-	-
AC-109	3.987	0.95	0.972	7	144.90	39.7	0.719	9	2.24	0.52	0.129	5	-	1.20 * 10 ²
NE-1141-2	5.013	1.48	0.164	7	161.11	59.3	0.381	9	1.86	0.19	1.00	7	+	5.02 * 10 ²
NE-1141-7	4.832	1.60	0.389	7	156.18	49.2	0.391	9	1.74	0.50	0.578	7	-	2.10 * 10 ²
NE-P-8	4.205	1.06	0.826	6	182.85	77.1	0.212	9	1.80	0.23	0.604	7	-	1.48 * 10 ³
OA-1	5.348	1.11	0.102	6	172.11	21.8	0.018	8	1.73	0.43	0.586	6	-	5.09 * 10 ²
Mock	4.003	1.20		7	138.95	40.4		9	1.86	0.19		7		2.63 * 10 ²
Neg. Control	6.963	0.42	0.000	7	203.83	31.0	0.002	9	0.69	0.63	0.02	7		1.73 * 10 ²

4. Discussion

Understanding the mode of action behind PGP in endophytes is a topic being addressed in an increasing number of scientific studies (Ali et al., 2014; Bonaldi et al., 2015; Qin et al., 2015). Manifesting in fluctuating efficacy, this knowledge gap represent a critical barrier to their application in biocontrol and biofertilizer products (Chen et al., 2016). Thus, with a growing interest in sustainable agricultural management practices, the emphasis on bridging this gap has never been stronger. Our aim was to study the link between *in vitro* screening of putative PGP traits and *in vivo* performance, to shed light on the nature of endophytes and investigate the potential of screening mediated selections.

The discussions of our findings have been divided in three parts, linking the *in vitro* screening results to 1) endophytic nature and persistency within the endosphere, 2) *in vivo* PGP and 3) *in vivo* suppression of *Verticillium* wilt disease.

Verifying the isolated strains as true competent endophytes was one of the initial steps in our experimental work. Together with the *in vitro* screening it allowed us to investigate if any of the selected traits were explicitly linked to this behaviour.

Majority of endophytes are facultative and their biphasic lifestyle include a free-living stage outside the plant, often in the rhizosphere (Hardoim et al., 2008). These soil-borne endophytes need to be competent colonizers of the rhizosphere to persist in this nutrient starved environment as saprophytes during periods where a host plant is unavailable (Berendsen et al., 2012). The ability of strains to biosynthesize selected CWDE, i.e. cellulase, pectinase and

xylanase were therefore not surprisingly found to be a common trait in the strains. However, the screening was conducted to investigate how many of the re-isolated strains exhibited the necessary CWDE toolbox to facilitate an active entry to plant endosphere. We observed that all eight re-isolated strains verified both morphologically and by 16S rRNA gene sequence exhibited capacity to biosynthesize all of the screened CWDE (Table 3.4). Our findings are, therefore, consistent with the literature, suggesting active entry as the primary mechanism of accessing the endosphere (Turner et al., 2014). Nonetheless, studies have yet to explicitly prove this theory. Amongst the selected strains, *B. thuringiensis* OA-1, *S. exfoliatus* AC-109, *S. albiacialis* NE-1141-2, *S. pratensis* NE-1141-7 and NE-P-8 possessed the traits consistent with a competent endophyte, i.e. CWDE to facilitate an active entry, and the capacity to persist for an extended period in the endosphere.

The re-isolation assay provided another piece of information besides verifying the endophytic nature, it gave us an insight in the strains influence on the cultivable microbiomes composition and diversity within the endosphere. Some of the strains (e.g. *S. albiacialis* NE-1141-2, *S. pratensis* NE-1141-7), seemingly stimulated a more diverse endophytic community with markedly different composition relative to the negative control. Other strains (*S. exfoliatus* AC-109, *B. thuringiensis* OA-1), however, drastically reduced the diversity and existed in essentially monoculture by exhibiting a strong competitive nature (Figure 3.5.1A, B). In a relatively closed system such as the greenhouse production of tomatoes, one could expect that a clear sovereignty of an inoculated PGP strain is not likely to pose an issue. However, in the field, crops are exposed to a more variable environment, loss in endophytic diversity and composition can, therefore, translate into a loss of resilience. To elaborate on this, plant stress is a likely signal, that can induce a behavioural change in some commensal endophytes, shifting to PGP endophytes capable of e.g. synthesizing ACC deaminase to alleviate abiotic stresses, or antagonize a phytopathogen (Ali et al., 2014). This conjecture is founded on the growing holistic perspective of the microbiota as a key player in plant functioning and plasticity (Vandenkoornhuyse et al., 2015).

Reproducibility of the re-isolation results observed in the PGP bioassay in cotton wool (table 3.5) were to a large degree unsuccessful. Countless of factors could be responsible for this inconsistency by interfering with the establishment of a stable relation with the plant (Chen et al., 2016). However, optimization of the surface sterilization protocol is recommended for further study, to reduce the amount of non-target endophytes killed by the procedure. Our observations, nonetheless, underline the extensive compositional change in microbiota likely to occur when inoculating a seed with an endophytic bacteria. Many *in vivo* studies conducted on endophytes do not investigate this effect, nor do they confirm the true endophytic nature of strains (Oteino et al., 2015; Xue et al., 2016). Re-isolation assay provide an platform, despite inconsistencies, for verification on a larger scale of inoculated strains prior to GFP tagging a selected few of particular interest (Bonaldi et al., 2015; Weyens et al., 2012).

Countless of traits are likely to contribute to PGP by bacterial endophytes, however, at present, only a limited set has been directly linked to this capacity. In our study, strains were screened for their ability to solubilize phosphorous, produce siderophores and degrade ACC.

In many agricultural soils phosphate compounds are present in abundance, but scarcely available as it exist in an insoluble form (Oteino et al., 2015). We, therefore, screened for

phosphate solubilisation as a direct mean of PGP by facilitating an increased availability of phosphate to the host plant. The ability to solubilize phosphate by secretion of organic acids was not observed in any of the *Streptomyces* sp., with *B. amyloliquefaciens* AC-35 as the only positive amongst selected strains. As this strain equivalently produced a consistently (non-significant) higher FW in the PGP assays (Table 3.5, Table 3.7 in supplementary material), our findings, show a correlation between phosphate solubilisation and the capacity to promote plant growth. Phosphate solubilisation has previously been linked to PGP in other *B. amyloliquefaciens* strains, supporting this observation (Soares et al., 2016). Application of such phosphate solubilizing PGPEs in biofertilizers is currently being presented as a sustainable alternative to the present-day surplus application of inorganic phosphate (Bhardwaj et al., 2014).

Bacterial biosynthesis of ACC deaminase is another example, and has commonly been accepted as a key traits in facilitating PGP (Glick, 2014), observed in several PGPEs (Qin et al., 2015; Tan et al., 2011). Degradation of ACC, a precursor to ethylene by an ACC deaminase results in an alleviation of stress that is largely detrimental to the plant. In our study the assay unfortunately failed, and the strains capacity to biosynthesize the enzyme remains unknown. The *Streptomyces* sp., strains ability to biosynthesize the deaminase is likely to contain an importance piece of the puzzle in our understanding of their PGP capacity, and assessment of the trait is strongly recommended. PGPE can modulate the host plant by several types of phytostimulation and studies has confirmed the biosynthesis of auxin in endophytic Actinobacteria (Long et al., 2008; Shi et al., 2009). Gene annotation of *B. amyloliquefaciens* AC-35 conducted in a previous study confirmed that it contains the genes for auxin biosynthesis (Nieuweteeg, 2015). Roots of the tomato plants in the PGP assay in soil were, therefore, rinsed to assess if the strains had an effect (PGP or architectural) on the root system. Seedlings treated with *B. amyloliquefaciens* AC-35 were observed to exhibit a slightly more branched root, consistent with auxin biosynthesis (figure 3.7D). To validate if auxin biosynthesis is connected to *B. amyloliquefaciens* AC-35 PGP capacity, a quantitative assay of its auxine biosynthesis is recommended for further study. As a last remark on the subject, PGPE have equivalently been observed to influence the plant hosts root development by regulating the auxine transporters in *Arabidopsis thaliana* (Wang et al., 2015). This markedly alteration in host root architecture by biosynthesis or interference with auxin transport can in some cases be beneficial to the plants nutritional uptake.

In spite of this consistent (non-significant) enhancement of plant growth by inoculation with *B. amyloliquefaciens* AC-35, re-isolation verification by 16S rRNA gene sequence comparison was unsuccessful. Efforts to GFP clone the strain has been undertaken in another study, but transformation resilience impeded the procedure (Unpublished data). In our study, none of the six selected *Streptomyces* sp., strains were observed to directly promote plant growth. These findings might be explained by the low population size observed in the re-isolation assay. Moreover, it remain unknown if a too harsh surface sterilization is the sole cause or if some unknown factor is interfering with their colonization efficacy. *S. exfoliatus* AC-109 was, nonetheless, successfully re-isolated in a large population (Figure 3.5.1B), and equivalently produced the highest average biomass in the PGP bioassay in soil (Table 3.7 in supplementary material). Siderophore production has previously been demonstrated to be directly linked to PGP capacity in a *Streptomyces* sp., enhancing the host plants uptake of iron (Rungin et al.,

2012; Wang et al., 1993). Our findings show no correlation between this trait and PGP capacity in the *Streptomyces* sp. strains. As the tomato seedlings were cultivated for a shorter period, and watered with a nutrient solution it is, reasonable to suggest that bacterial mediated iron acquisition under these conditions was not advantageous to the plant host.

Promotion of plant growth is not singularly a product of direct interaction between the bacterial endophyte and its plant host. It can equivalently be mediated indirectly by the antagonism of a phytopathogen, reducing its detrimental effect to the plant. Promotion of plant growth by endophytic *Streptomyces* sp. is often indirect, mediated by the vast arsenal of secondary metabolites with antifungal activity found in the genus (Cao et al., 2016; Chater, 2006; Fialho de Oliveira et al., 2010). In our work we selected *V. dahliae*, causative agent of Verticillium wilt disease, as it commonly occurred in the greenhouses where the tomato stem material was harvested. *V. dahliae* invades the host plant through the roots leading to an extensive colonization of the xylem tissue, giving cause to wilting (Fradin and Thomma, 2006). In consideration of this, the isolated stem endophytes equivalently colonize this niche making the pathogen-endophyte interaction a theoretical possibility. To investigate which traits mediate the *Streptomyces* sp. strains ability to suppress Verticillium wilt disease *in vivo*, these were screened for their production of hydrolytic enzymes (chitinase, protease), siderophore and *in vitro* antagonistic activity.

In the fungal recovery assay, *S. griseolus* AC-34 was the only strain found to significantly reduce *V. dahliae* colonization *in vivo* (Figure 3.81). Our *in vitro* screening results revealed a correlation between the production of chitinase and protease, and this activity in *S. griseolus* AC-34 (Table 3.4). However, chitinase production is a conserved trait within the *Streptomyces* genus, as it facilitate the breakdown of e.g. fungal cell-wall for nutritional uptake (Chater, 2006). Nonetheless, chitinase had been observed in some *Streptomyces* sp., including the closely related *S. halstedii* (indistinctable on the 16S rRNA gene sequence comparison) to exhibit direct antifungal activity (Hoster et al., 2005). Moreover, proteases have been observed in some *Streptomyces* sp. to also exhibit antifungal activities and significantly reduce spore germination, adhesion and hyphal extension among others (Palaniyandi et al., 2013; Singh and Chhatpar, 2011). Our findings, therefore, recommend further study to investigate if an antifungal chitinase and or protease is involved in this *in vivo* suppression of Verticillium wilt disease by *S. griseolus* AC-34. The minor inhibitory capacity observed *in vitro* relative to the *in vivo* suppression infer a host-triggered response, such as induction of systemic resistance. PGP rhizosphere *Streptomyces* sp. have been observed to enhance defence-related response in *V. dahliae* infected cotton (Xue et al. 2016), this is equivalently a possible mode of action in *S. griseolus* AC-34.

Inoculation with *S. griseolus* AC-34 had, nonetheless, only a minute positive effect on tomato seedling growth and leaf coverage despite the significant reduction in *V. dahliae* colonization (Table 3.8, Table 3.81 in supplementary material). *S. rishiriensis* AC-107, in contrary, significantly promoted growth and leaf coverage, while it had no effect on *V. dahliae* colonization. PGP was, therefore, not linked to suppression of the disease by *S. rishiriensis* AC-107, but by an unknown set of traits. Hypothetically, the biotic stress induced by *V. dahliae* colonization might have stimulated a behavioural change in *S. rishiriensis* AC-107 from a non-beneficial to a PGP endophyte.

Another interesting observation was the consistent reduction of FW by *S. griseolus* AC-34 in the PGP bioassays, suggesting that the strain has a detrimental effect to the host plant (Table 3.5, Table 3.7 in supplementary material). Phytopathogenicity is, however, a rarity within the *Streptomyces* genus, with *S. scabies* causative agent of potato scab as the most known case (Loria et al., 2006). Consequently to the definition of endophytes cited initially, any microorganism isolated from the endosphere causing, at any point of its life cycle, apparent harm to its host plant is not an endophyte. It is nonetheless difficult to separate latent pathogens from endophytes, as unknown environmental cues signal the behavioural change from commensal or beneficial to detrimental. Our observations, therefore, engage in the continuing debate regarding the definition of endophytes, and it remains unknown if *S. griseolus* AC-34 is directly causing “apparent harm” to the host plant, and hence should not be regarded as an endophyte. In the presence of *V. dahliae*, our observations, nonetheless, support the classification of *S. griseolus* AC-34 as an endophyte.

The large variability observed in the initial Verticillium wilt disease assay could equivalently suggest a differential colonization success, clouding the suppressive capacity of some strains (Figure 3.81). Several of the isolate treatments (e.g. *S. griseolus* AC-34, *S. exfoliatus* AC-109, *S. albiacialis* NE-1141-2) show tendency to form two groupings in particularly the FW results, a higher and lower. This grouping is, however, not visible in the fungal recovery assay results. These observations support a differential colonization of PGPES but do not infer that they achieve this promotion of growth by suppression of Verticillium wilt disease. Attempt to investigate if the strains were present in the larger plants and absent in the smaller, however, failed due to a contaminated PBS buffer.

Re-isolation of the strains was, largely unsuccessful in the suppression of Verticillium wilt disease assay as only *S. albiacialis* NE-1141-2 could be verified, and in a limited population (table 3.8). As *S. griseolus* AC-34 was isolated from tomato root, and never successfully re-isolated from stem, this suggest that the strain is either strictly confined to the root tissue or simply a rhizosphere bacteria. In regard to the other strains, inability to re-isolate them could suggest that *V. dahliae* is a more successful competitor in the xylem niche.

These observations do not support the strong association between endophytic *Streptomyces* and plants implied by the observations of a Streptomycetacea family enrichment in *A. thaliana* endosphere (Lundberg et al., 2013). The selected *Streptomyces* sp., strains in this study did not seem to confer unique PGP capacities or ability to persist in the endosphere, relative to the other endophytic strains studied. Our findings did, therefore, not shed further light on the underlying reason for this enrichment.

Our results conclude that the link between putative PGP traits and *in vivo* promotion of plant growth is weak, but enable us to infer a potential mode of action to be further investigated. To make this link, our observations emphasise the necessity of a re-isolation verification step. We found that seed inoculation with an endophytic *Streptomyces* sp. had an extensive effect on composition and diversity of the tomato endosphere microbiome. However, none of the six endophytic *Streptomyces* sp. were observed to significantly promote plant growth in a consistent manner or suppress Verticillium wilt disease in tomato. However, *S. griseolus* AC-34 significantly reduced *V. dahliae* colonization without enhancing the biomass of the infected

tomato seedlings. Our results showed a correlation between chitinase and protease production, however, further studies are necessary to verify if these are linked to the *in vivo* suppression. As a last remark these observations confirm the complexity of studying endophytes, and advocate the necessity of a holistic perspective to unveil their role in plant functioning.

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Supplementary Material

Table 3.7: Fresh weight (FW), Leaf coverage and re-isolation results of the tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum* cv. Moneymaker) seedling bioassay in soil 28 days after seed inoculation with endophytic bacterial strains. Paired t-test was conducted on strains mean relative to Neg. control with $P \leq 0.05$. SD = Standard deviation

Strain	Fresh weight			Leaf Coverage			Re-isolation	
	Mean (g)	SD (n = 9)	Paired t-test p-value	Mean (cm ²)	SD (n = 9)	Paired t-test p-value	Stem colonization	Total Population size Per g FW
AC-34	1.938	0.76	0.040	73.33	33.4	0.513	+	$5.9 * 10^2$
AC-35	2.416	0.59	0.873	88.25	30.4	0.689	+	$5.38 * 10^2$
AC-107	1.949	0.21	0.140	76.87	12.3	0.439	+	$4.34 * 10^3$
AC-109 (n=8)	2.66	0.44	0.812	90.51	12.4	0.531	+	$3.24 * 10^3$
NE-1141-2	1.834	0.34	0.081	65.90	11.6	0.183	+	$3.01 * 10^2$
NE-1141-7	2.400	0.48	0.811	88.17	18.7	0.806	+	$5.18 * 10^2$
NE-P-8	2.356	0.50	0.783	80.16	17.7	0.772	+	$9.85 * 10^2$
OA-1	2.608	0.56	0.805	94.14	16.6	0.38	+	$3.18 * 10^2$
Neg. Control	2.482	0.98		83.22	33.2			$4.85 * 10^2$

Table 3.81: Fresh weight, Leaf coverage, disease severity and re-isolation results of the first *Verticillium* wilt disease suppression assay on tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum* cv. Moneymaker) seedlings in soil, 37 days after seed inoculation with endophytic strain, and 23 days after root dip in *Verticillium dahliae* spore solution. Paired t-test was conducted on strain mean relative to Mock treatment with $P \leq 0.05$. Mock is inoculated with *V. dahliae* solely. SD = Standard deviation.

Strain	Fresh weight			Leaf Coverage			Fungal Recovery		
	Mean (g)	SD	Paired t-test p-value	Mean (cm ²)	SD	Paired t-test p-value	Mean	SD	Paired t-test p-value
AC-34	2.693	1.12	0.515	101.88	46.3	0.269	1.40	0.55	0.031
AC-35	2.716	1.13	0.425	98.56	38.7	0.358	1.89	0.38	0.471
AC-107	3.295	0.89	0.036	110.07	28.2	0.04	1.98	0.25	0.753
AC-109	2.427	1.03	0.969	89.49	35.4	0.712	1.98	0.23	0.746
NE-1141-2	2.271	1.24	0.672	78.83	37.8	0.665	1.78	0.61	0.273
NE-1141-7	2.603	0.68	0.536	94.86	18.1	0.201	2.02	0.46	1.000
NE-P-8	2.295	0.85	0.590	90.65	35.1	0.642	1.69	0.59	0.121
OA-1	2.604	1.34	0.763	96.89	44.1	0.511	1.43	0.80	0.115
Mock	2.448	0.38		84.66	10.2		2.02	0.29	
Neg. Control	4.469	0.74	0.000	149.6	22.0	0.000	1.15	0.81	0.013